

TABLE III (contd.).

Unaccounted for.		Remarks.
C, 0.19 g.		
O ₂ , 0.26 g.	340 c.c. CO	Excess of H ₂ and deficit in CO should be accounted for in the same way as in Table II.
H ₂ , 0.04 g. in excess	450 c.c. H ₂	

While this investigation was in progress, Fischer and Koch (*Brennstoff-Chemie*, 1932 **13**, 61) published results obtained with the following catalysts:—Co + 18% Th or Co + 15% Mn, precipitated with alkaline carbonate. By continuous circulation of gases, the yield of liquid hydrocarbons approached 71% of the theoretical. In our experimental data recorded in Table III it will be seen that a single passage of water-gas above our catalyst at a space velocity of 59 gave 48.3% of the theoretical yield calculated on the basis of the equation,

This catalyst therefore appears to be very efficient one.

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Addition of Compounds Containing Reactive Methylene Group with Phenylvinylketone.

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In a work to be published later on, large quantities of phenylvinylketone were obtained as a bye-product. Since it combines very readily with substances containing reactive methylene group, it can be used for making saturated ketonic compounds which are unsaturated in the β -position and which it is difficult to prepare in any other manner. Allen and Bridgess (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **51**, 2151) and Kohler (*Amer. Chem. J.*, 1909, **42**, 375) have also done some work in this line. The additive properties of this $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated ketone with substances containing reactive methylene group, e.g.

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(i) acetoacetic ester, (ii) desoxybenzoin, (iii) phenylacetone and (iv) dibenzylketone have been studied in this paper. All these substances added themselves at the double bond of phenylvinylketone; in some cases, however, secondary reactions take place with the elimination of a molecule of water.

Acetoacetic ester gave with phenylvinylketone in the presence of sodium ethoxide an additive product (I or Ia), but it very easily eliminated one molecule of water producing an unsaturated cyclic ketonic acid ester (II), which on saponification resulted in the unsaturated ketone (III). On treating with ozone in chloroform, (III) gave an ozonide which decomposed with water to benzoic and succinic acids.

Desoxybenzoin reacted with phenylvinylketone in the presence of sodium ethoxide forming a 1:5-diketone (IV).

Benzylmethylketone and dibenzylketone gave instead of the expected addition products (V) and (VI), the unsaturated cyclic ketones (VII) and (VIII).

EXPERIMENTAL.

Addition of acetoacetic ester with phenylvinylketone.—(a). An equimolecular mixture of acetoacetic ester and phenylvinylketone (each 9 g.), kept cold by ice, was treated with sodium ethylate (1%, 10 c.c.). After one hour the solution was acidified with hydrochloric acid, extracted with ether, the ether removed and the residue distilled in vacuum at 12 mm., when the following fractions were obtained:—

- (i) till 100° (7 g.), chiefly unreacted raw material.
- (ii) 200-205° (8 g.), phenylcyclohexenonecarboxylic acid ester.
- (iii) 300° (1 g.), chiefly polymerised phenylvinylketone.

(b). To an equimolecular mixture of dimethylaminopropiophenone (18 g.) and acetoacetic ester (13 g.) were added, every second or third day, 10 c.c. of 1% sodium ethylate solution. After a fortnight the whole of the mixture was acidified with hydrochloric acid and extracted with ether. The acidified aqueous solution contained about 50-55% of the unchanged dimethylaminopropiophenone which could be recovered by making the solution alkaline with caustic soda.

From the residue of the ethereal extract, there appeared, after 24 hours, α -acetyl- γ -benzoylbutyric acid ester (I) which crystallised from alcohol in the form of colourless prismatic needles, yield 2.8 g.

By the distillation of the oily portion in vacuum at 12 mm. the following fractions were obtained:—

- (i) till 100° (5 g.). Raw material, e.g., acetoacetic ester.
- (ii) 200-205° (6.5 g.). When allowed to stand for a week or so there appeared crystals of phenylcyclohexenone (III). The oily portion consisted of phenylcyclohexenonecarboxylic acid ester (II).
- (iii) 300° (0.5 g.). Polymerised phenylvinylketone.

Ethyl α -acetyl- γ -benzoylbutyric acetate was obtained by the method (b) in the form of prismatic needles from alcohol, m.p. 120°. (Found: C, 68.54; H, 7.0. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 68.68; H, 6.92 per cent).

On heating this ester at 200° for 2 hours, alcohol and CO_2 were given off and from the residue phenylcyclohexenone was obtained by crystallisation from petrol ether, m.p. 64°

Monozime.—A solution of diketonic acid ester (I) (0.5 g.) in alcohol (15 c.c.), was mixed and heated on a water-bath with an

aqueous solution of hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.8 g.) and potassium acetate (0.4 g.). The insoluble oxime was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 160-61°. (Found: N, 5.23. $C_{15}H_{19}O_4N$ requires N, 5.05 per cent).

4-Phenyl-6-keto- $\Delta^{3,5}$ -cyclohexene-1-carboxylic acid ester (II) was obtained by the fractional distillation of the oily portion mentioned above under (b), b.p. 200-205°/12 mm. (Found: C, 74.03; H, 6.86. $C_{15}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 73.75; H, 6.61 per cent).

Experiments performed in order to get the semicarbazone and *p*-nitrophenylhydrazone of this ester always resulted, even at low temperatures, in the saponification and splitting up of CO_2 and the formation of the corresponding derivative of phenylcyclohexenone.

5-Phenyl- $\Delta^{5,8}$ -cyclohexenone-1 (III).—This was obtained through the saponification of phenylcyclohexenoncarboxylic acid ester (II). The ester was warmed for a short time with a little excess of an aqueous solution of *N*-KOH. The solution was acidified with hydrochloric acid and then extracted with ether. The residue on removing the solvent crystallised from petrol as prismatic leaflets, m.p. 64° (b.p. 172-73 /12 mm). (Found: C, 84.06; H, 7.11. $C_{12}H_{12}ON$ requires C, 83.69; H, 7.0 per cent).

In chloroform solution, it gave an addition product with a molecule of bromine, but it was not possible to crystallise the product.

The oxime was prepared by warming a solution of phenylcyclohexenone (0.5 g.) in alcohol (2 c.c.) with a concentrated aqueous solution of hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.2 g.) and potassium acetate (0.3 g.) for 6 hours on a water-bath. It was crystallised from 50% alcohol as colourless crystals, m.p. 117-18°. (Found: N, 7.17. $C_{12}H_{13}ON$ requires N, 7.48 per cent).

The semicarbazone was prepared in the usual manner and crystallised either from alcohol or acetic acid, m.p. 222°. (Found: C, 68.07; H, 6.45; N, 18.17. $C_{13}H_{15}ON_3$ requires C, 68.10; H, 6.59; N, 18.34 per cent). The same semicarbazone was obtained from phenylcyclohexenone carboxylic acid ester (II).

The *p*-nitrophenylhydrazone was prepared in the usual manner and crystallised from alcohol in orange red prismatic crystals, m.p. 184-85°. (Found: N, 13.44. $C_{18}H_{17}O_2N_3$ requires N, 13.68 per cent).

Oxidation of phenylcyclohexenone through ozone.—The unsaturated ketone (III) (5 g.) was dissolved in dry chloroform (100 c.c.) and a fairly rapid current of ozone was allowed to bubble through the solution, till it became blue (8 hours), when the solid ozonide

crystallised out. After evaporating the chloroform, the ozonide was allowed to be decomposed by adding water (30 c.c.) and after 2 days, the solid crystals were sucked off and crystallised from hot water, m.p. 121°, and gave no depression with benzoic acid. The filtrate was shaken with ether in order to get rid of the dissolved benzoic acid. After evaporating the solvent the residue was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 183° and gave no depression with succinic acid, yield succinic acid (2 g.) and benzoic acid (3 g.).

Polymerised phenylvinylketone.—The fraction obtained with b.p. 300°/12 mm. from the addition product of acetoacetic ester and phenylvinylketone was kept under petroleum for some days. The crystals thus separated were purified through crystallisation from alcohol, m.p. 108°. [Found: C, 81.93; H, 6.10. $(C_9H_8O)_x$ requires C, 81.78; H, 6.11 per cent].

1:5 Diketo-1:2:5-triphenylpentane (IV).—A solution of phenylvinylketone (1.4 g.) and desoxybenzoin (2 g.) in methyl alcohol (10 c.c.) was treated with a concentrated solution of sodium methylate (0.05 g. sodium) under ice-cooling, when crystals separated which were recrystallised from methyl alcohol m.p. 97-98°, yield, 2.2 g. (Found: C, 84.27; H, 6.53. $C_{23}H_{20}O_2$ requires C, 84.11; H, 6.1 per cent).

The *monoxime* crystallised from a small quantity of alcohol, m.p. 125-26°. (Found: C, 80.59; H, 5.92; N, 4.36. $C_{23}H_{21}O_2N$ requires C, 80.70; H, 5.89; N, 4.09 per cent).

2:5 Diphenyl- $\Delta^{5,6}$ -cyclohexenone-1 (VII).—A solution of phenylvinylketone (6.5 g.) and benzylmethylketone (6.5 g.) in methyl alcohol (10 c.c.) was treated under ice-cooling with a concentrated solution of sodium methylate (1 c.c.) when a vigorous reaction ensued. The fraction obtained by distillation at 240-260°/12 mm. gave crystals, which were recrystallised from alcohol and a small quantity of acetic acid, m.p. 149-50° yield 20%. (Found: C, 87.34; H, 6.26. $C_{18}H_{16}O$ requires C, 87.05; H, 6.5 per cent).

2:5:6-Triphenyl- $\Delta^{5,6}$ -cyclohexenone-1 (VIII).—A solution of phenylvinylketone (6.5 g.) and dibenzylketone (10.5 g.) in methyl alcohol (10 c.c.) was treated under ice-cooling with a saturated solution of sodium methylate (1 c.c.) when a vigorous reaction ensued. The triphenylcyclohexenone which separated out was crystallised as prismatic needles from alcohol, m.p. 135°, yield 8 g. (Found: C, 88.71; H, 6.36. $C_{24}H_{20}O$ requires C, 88.84; H, 6.21 per cent).